

A Study on Impact of Social Media among the College Students with Special Reference in Dharmapuri (Dt)

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Abstract

Social media is a catch –all term for a variety of internet application that allows users to create content and interact with each other .this interaction can take many forms but some common types include;

1. *Sharing links to interesting content produced by third parties.*
2. *Public updates to a profile, including information on current activities and even location data.*
3. *Sharing photos, videos and posts.*
4. *Commenting on the photos, posts, updates, videos and links shared by others.*

Meaning of Social Media

Refers to techniques that target social networks and applications to spread brand awareness or promote particular products, social media marketing campaigns usually center around.

1. Establishing a social media presence on major platforms.
2. Creating shareable content and advertorials .
3. Cultivating customer feedback throughout the campaign through surveys and contest

Social media marketing is perceived as a more targeted type of advertising and is therefore believed to be very effective in creating brand awareness.

Objective of Study

1. To understand the awareness level of usage of different social networking sites.
2. To find out the relevance of information received from social networking sites.
3. To know the impact of social networking sites among the college students.

Limitation

1. The survey conducted may not be considered as comprehensive as only limited respondents could be contacted because of the time constraint.

2. Objectives and the purposes of the study and the questions had to be explained to the their response may be biased.

Statement of the Problem

1. A statement of problem is used in research work as a claim that outlines the problem addressed by a study.
2. The good research problem should address and existing gap in knowledge in the field and lead to future research of the entire population.

Research Methodology

A system of models, process and techniques used to find the results of a research problem is called a research methodology.

Research Desgin

Research design is the outline of the study that guides the researcher in collecting and analyzing the data, which is the important part of the project

Source of Data

Primary data

The primary data are those which are collected for first and a fresh hand thus happen to be original in character . The sources of information that a researcher should tap way with his interest and types sources .The data from field sources may be collected from person. primary data may be made through either by complete enumerations or sampling survey method.

Secondary data

Secondary data consist of information that already exists somewhere, which has been collected for specific purpose in this study. The secondary data for this study was collected from various books, websites and journals.

Sample Size

The sample size selected for the study is 35 respondents in Dharmapuri .sampling technique used for the study is simple random sampling method.

Tool & Techniques

1. Percentage analysis
2. Simple percentage

Percentage Analysis

Percentage analysis refers to a special type of ratio percentage is used in making comparison between two percentage analysis two or more series of data. Percentages are used to describe the relationship between the data

$$\text{Percentage(\%)} = \frac{\text{NUMBER OF RESPONDERTS}}{\text{TOTL NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS}} \times 100$$

Table Education Qualification

S.No	Educational qualification	No .of respondents	Percentage(%)
1	Ug	11	31%
2	Pg	14	40%
3	Other	10	29%
Total		35	100%

Sources: Primary data

Chart - Educational qualification

Findings, Suggestion and Conclusion

Findings

Majority (39%) of the respondents are coming under the category PG of level.

Suggestion

Seminars should be organized in the colleges to enlighten the students more about the possible implications of social media using on their academic performance.

Conclusion

The purpose of this research work was to examine the social media networking sites patterns of students and the impact of social networking sites on their lives and behavior .It is found that social networking sites are very popular among the students with the majority of the stating that they are active members of social networks .